

THE ROLE OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES IN INVESTMENT ATTRACTIVENESS

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All-round development of the country, including the stable growth of its macroeconomic and microeconomic indicators, the increase of the share of exports in the balance of goods together with the saturation of the market, the increase in the level of well-being of the population, the country's appearance among the powerful countries in the world. The special economic zones established in the country contribute to the increase in the volume of investments attracted to the country and its comprehensive development.

A special economic zone is an area with defined boundaries and a special legal regime, specially allocated for the purpose of attracting foreign investments and local investments, high technologies and management experience for the rapid socio-economic development of the respective area. Special economic zones can be organized as follows:

- free economic zones;
- special scientific and technological zones;
- touristic and recreational zones;
- free trade zones;
- special industrial zones.

SEZs have several advantages in attracting investors. SEZs often offer various benefits to domestic and foreign investors, such as tax breaks, reduced tariffs, and simplified regulatory processes. These benefits reduce the cost of doing business and increase profitability, making the country more attractive to investors. SEZs are usually established with excellent infrastructure, including transport, utility and communication networks. This well-developed infrastructure reduces operational difficulties and increases the efficiency of businesses operating in the area. It should be noted that SEZs are usually intended for export-oriented production. SEZs create a favorable environment for production and export, helping enterprises to expand their market presence and generate foreign exchange for the country. Furthermore, SEZs often create many employment opportunities both directly within the regions and indirectly through supporting networks. This employment growth can improve the local economy and increase consumer spending, creating a virtuous cycle of economic

growth. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI): SEZs can attract significant foreign direct investment by offering a business-friendly environment. The increase in direct investment brings not only capital, but also technology transfer, managerial expertise and access to global markets.

In addition, SEZs help diversify the country's economic base by promoting the development of new industries in the country and reducing dependence on traditional industries. Such diversification can increase economic stability. Another noteworthy aspect of SEZs is that concentration of enterprises in SEZs can increase innovation and competitiveness. Companies benefit from proximity to suppliers, customers and competitors, which leads to increased productivity and innovation through collaboration and competition. SEZs can serve as a testing ground for broader economic reforms. Successful policies implemented in SEZs can then be replicated in the rest of the country, leading to overall economic improvement. Global integration: SEZs help integrate a country into the global economy by facilitating trade and investment ties. Such integration can lead to the growth of exports, saturation of the national market with quality goods, and more stable economic growth and development.

A number of works are being carried out in our country to establish SEZs in our country, to give many benefits and preferences to entrepreneurs and investors operating in them, with understanding of the national development of SEZs, especially their role in investment attractiveness. The adoption of the Law No. 604 of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Special Economic Zones" in our republic on February 17, 2020, many state regulations in the field of organizing the operation of special economic zones and their development it is noteworthy that reforms are being carried out. According to it, the development of the special economic zone is carried out in accordance with the program, which includes:

- creation of production infrastructure;
- to provide engineering-communication and road transport infrastructure development programs;
- creation of market infrastructure;
- a complex of measures to attract foreign investments and local investments in accordance with the activity and sectoral specialization of the special economic zone.

Financial support of the development program of the special economic zone is carried out at the expense of the zone's own resources, private sources, funds of the State budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan, international financial

institutions and foreign government financial organizations, as well as other sources not prohibited by law.

In the formation of the state investment programs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the financial support of the engineering-communication and road transport infrastructure development programs of the special economic zones should be provided.

According to the Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as of October 1, 2023, there are 819 economic zones in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and 5196 enterprises and organizations operate in them. Among them there are: 22 special (free) economic zones, 323 small industrial zones, 24 technological parks and 450 clusters. and the number of enterprises and organizations within them was 752 in SEZ, 2488 in KSZ, 1501 in expoparks and 455 in clusters. There are significant differences in the number of SEZs operating in our country across regions (Figure 1).

It is worth noting that the SEZs of our country have enterprises operating in various fields and industries. This plays a very important role in the diversification of our country's economy. The types of products produced by SEZs and their industrial enterprises in our country are as follows: production of motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers - 26.4%, production of food products - 17.4%, metallurgical industry - 15.2%, production of rubber and plastic products - 9%, production of chemical products - 5.1%, production of textile products - 4.8%, production of other non-metallic mineral products - 4.6%, computers, electronic and optical products production - 4.4%, production of finished metal products excluding machines and equipment - 3.4%, and production of other types of industrial products - 9.7%.

Figure 1. The number of SEZs in the Republic of Uzbekistan, by regions

During 2023, the total production volume of industrial products in our country is 55229.9 billion. amounted to 27,545.6 billion soums. products produced in SEZ made up soums. Taking into account the importance of SEZs in the country's economy and development, the economic and social interests of the population, it is necessary to further improve the system of SEZs, their activities and the privileges granted to them in Uzbekistan.

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